

Seasonal incidence of sheath rot in Thanjavur Delta, India

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Seasonal incidence of sheath rot was studied in 1977 and 1978 in 20 planting series covering the entire cropping period of the Thanjavur Delta area of Tamil Nadu.

The first planting was done on 15 June and the last on 25 December with a 10-day interval between plantings. Eight varieties or cultivars were evaluated in 1977 and 10 in 1978 for relative resistance. Sheath rot incidence was recorded at the ninth crop stage. The disease incidence (transformed value for percentage) for 1977 is given in Table 1 and that for 1978 is in Table 2.

Sheath rot incidence was extremely high on crops planted from 15 June to 15 August 1977 and from 15 June to 5 August 1978, the planting period of the first crop (kuruvai). It seems sheath rot needs to be controlled only in the first crop season to overcome heavy yield loss.

None of the variants tested was resistant. ■

Table 1. Seasonal incidence of sheath rot in Thanjavur Delta, India, 1977.

Date of planting	Incidence (%)								Mean ^a
	ADT31	IET1722	Tainan 3 (M)	AD11585	Pusa33-18	IR26	IR20	Bhavani	
15 Jun	40.1	35.4	22.9	42.7	36.5	55.5	54.6	43.2	42.2
25 Jun	42.2	35.5	30.3	52.8	35.2	45.5	31.0	33.1	38.2
5 Jul	51.3	52.9	34.7	49.5	41.1	38.7	40.1	30.1	42.3
15 Jul	55.1	59.0	57.4	50.4	51.6	33.3	34.9	30.5	46.5
25 Jul	45.4	50.6	51.4	44.6	39.8	52.2	49.3	50.6	48.1
5 Aug	31.8	47.2	46.4	36.7	32.6	48.8	45.4	49.2	43.0
5 Sep	22.8	14.0	20.5	20.7	18.3	15.8	18.9	13.2	18.0
5 Oct	41.3	37.9	36.6	17.0	36.2	35.3	29.8	19.8	31.7
5 Nov	14.0	10.2	12.4	9.8	10.3	12.7	12.3	11.2	11.6
5 Dec	17.9	9.8	9.8	8.5	10.2	7.3	11.1	11.7	10.8
Mean	27.2	24.6	24.2	25.4	23.1	25.8	25.3	23.9	
C.D.	Variety		Period	Variety x period					
	1.68		2.65	7.50					

^a Data on the maximum incidence of sheath rot observed in the first 6 plantings (15 Jun-5 Aug) are given in full. Where incidence continued to decrease, only data in the first planting of the given month are included. The actual mean of 20 plantings is given as the mean for varieties.

Table 2. Seasonal incidence of sheath rot in Thanjavur Delta, India, 1978.

Date of planting	Incidence (%)										Mean ^a
	ADT31	IET2881	4-1-11-1	AD6380	AD5620	AD54-1	AS3827	CRM 105747	Bhavani	IR20	
15 Jun	37.3	33.8	33.4	38.1	33.9	56.4	33.7	25.5	38.1	35.8	34.8
25 Jun	35.1	27.9	34.6	47.2	30.3	42.1	39.5	33.9	30.9	40.0	36.2
5 Jul	38.9	37.3	36.7	52.9	38.5	55.8	53.5	40.1	37.6	43.0	43.4
15 Jul	43.2	39.1	33.6	45.1	43.0	45.7	49.2	43.2	52.2	50.7	44.1
25 Jul	49.2	41.4	45.3	36.1	50.0	38.9	41.8	46.3	45.8	55.6	43.0
5 Aug	39.5	43.0	35.5	34.1	40.5	33.3	45.0	40.7	47.0	45.0	40.3
5 Sep	24.5	23.2	25.5	17.4	25.0	24.6	16.5	17.2	17.2	27.5	22.7
5 Oct	25.5	17.0	18.8	7.6	13.3	8.6	12.8	8.6	20.0	14.0	14.6
5 Nov	8.5	18.0	8.4	7.3	11.5	6.9	6.5	9.0	11.8	10.4	9.9
5 Dec	4.1	7.2	4.1	4.1	4.1	4.1	4.1	4.1	4.1	4.1	4.4
Mean	21.2	21.9	21.2	19.6	20.8	21.7	20.5	18.0	21.8	23.9	
C.D.	Variety			Planting	Variety x Period						
	0.62			0.83	2.62						

^a Data on the maximum incidence of sheath rot observed in the first 6 plantings (15 Jun-5 Aug) are given in full. Where incidence continued to decrease, only data in the first planting of the given month are included. The actual mean of 20 plantings is given as the mean for varieties.